

THE ROLE OF MODERN APPROACHES IN DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE PHYSICS TEACHERS

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В данной статье раскрываются возможности развития профессиональных компетенций будущих учителей физики на основе современных подходов, тем самым повышая качество образования и достигая эффективности.

Ключевые слова: современный подход, STEM-подход, модель 5E, модель 3C+1E, навыки XXI века, 4K-подход, креативность, коммуникативность, коллаборация, критическое мышление;

This article reveals the possibilities of developing the professional competencies of future physics teachers based on modern approaches, thereby improving the quality of education and achieving effectiveness.

Keywords: modern approach, STEM approach, 5E model, 3C+1E model, 21st century skills, 4K approach, creativity, communication, collaboration, critical thinking;

In today's rapidly developing world, the main goal of teaching physics is to train qualified pedagogical personnel who meet the requirements of the time, are competitive in the world market, find their place, possess deep knowledge and perfect professional competencies. According to modern educational standards, physics teachers must have deep knowledge in their field, be able to effectively use modern approaches, establish interactive communication with students, and effectively manage the educational process. They also need to be able to use methods that develop students' independent thinking skills and involve them in research activities. These requirements are connected with the natural complexity of physics and the need to form a scientific worldview in students. From this point of view, since physics is a science that studies natural phenomena and laws, students need to explain physical phenomena visually, interactively, and experimentally. Therefore, future physics teachers should be aware of modern approaches, use them effectively, and know how to use approaches that can demonstrate phenomena and processes. The main goal of using these modern approaches is aimed at forming students' scientific thinking, analyzing life problems based on physical laws, developing practical skills, and acquiring 21st-century competencies. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 No. UP-5847 "On Approving the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" on the introduction of these modern approaches into the educational process provides for the upbringing of highly qualified, independently thinking youth with modern knowledge and skills in harmony with international standards and national traditions, strengthening attention to the quality of personnel training in humanitarian and pedagogical fields, forming the skills of applying modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process among students studying in this field, paying special attention to the development of STEM fields, improving the quality of educational literature, and simplifying the procedure for creating modern educational literature [1].

Currently, the approaches and methods of the USA, Cambridge, Finland, and Singapore in the organization of education are being implemented in the education system of our country.

Educational programs and teaching methods in these countries are being popularized internationally. In particular, if we talk about the STEM approach, STEM is an educational technology of the USA. The STEM approach was first developed in 2000 at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in the USA and was initially implemented in general education schools in the USA.

STEM is an interdisciplinary integrated approach based on design educational technology. The design educational technology is implemented in six stages (question, discussion, design, construction, commissioning, and improvement). [2].

Figure 1. Components of the STEM approach

Furthermore, one of the approaches that directly helps to develop students' research skills is the 5E model. What is the 5E model? How can the 5E model be used in the teaching process?

The 5E model is a methodological approach used to organise the learning process effectively and ensure students' active participation. This model is divided into five stages, each of which is designed to meet the different needs of students during the learning process.

Figure 2. 5E model stages

Along with this, we can cite the 3C+1E model as one of the modern approaches that directly contributes to the formation of students' research and scientific analysis skills. The 3C+1E model consists of four main stages.

Figure 3. 3C+1E model stages

These modern approaches serve as a key factor in the formation of 21st-century skills in students.

The 4K approach, as its name suggests, includes four principles:

Collaboration - working together to achieve a common goal.

Communicativeness (communication) - the exchange of ideas and opinions using questions.

Creative thinking (creativity) - testing new approaches to problem-solving.

Critical thinking is a new approach to problems. [3, 4].

Figure 4. 4K skill-building approaches

On these approaches, scientists from our country and foreign states, such as Margaret Honey and D.E. Kanter [2], R.W. Bybee [3; p. 49], J.R. Polanin [4; p. 120], B. Trilling and C. Fadel [5], D. D. Minner et al. [6; pp. 474–496], E. L. Duran and L. B. Duran [7; pp. 49–58], D. Melgarejo [8; pp. 211–226], I. Sotakova [9; pp. 68–80] on the integration of the core principles of the STEM approach into the teacher preparation process, and on enhancing students'

scientific literacy within the BSCS (Biological Sciences Curriculum Study) framework based on the 5E model, that the 5E model yields superior results compared to the traditional 'lecturing + note-taking' methods, the development of a conceptual model for fostering these competencies within the education system based on the 4K approach, developing students' analytical competencies in European and North American schools using the 5E model, Research has been conducted on organizing laboratory sessions in the natural sciences using the 5E model, and on the positive impact of lessons organized on the basis of the 5E model on students' cognitive activity and inquiry skills.

The importance of these modern approaches is that they not only ensure pupils' high literacy in subjects, but also that future teachers learn how to link their subjects with real-life situations, organise experiential learning, use interactive and digital resources, and develop 4K competencies. Taking these aspects into account, our country's education system and State Education Standards have defined the "New Uzbekistan begins at the school threshold" concept as a way to achieve high results in international assessment programmes. Firstly, these experiences enable higher education institutions in pedagogy to strengthen the integration of theory and practice in the educational process, to develop competencies that meet international assessment criteria, and to bring the educational process closer to global standards.

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